

STUDIES ON THE RELATION BETWEEN CHEMICAL CONSTITUTION AND
ULTRAVIOLET ABSORPTION SPECTRA OF OPTICALLY ACTIVE AND
RACEMIC COMPOUNDS. PART IV. CORRELATION OF ABSORPTION
MAXIMA AND CHARACTERISTIC WAVE-LENGTHS OF SOME
ARYLIMINO- AND ARYLAMINO-CAMPBOR DERIVATIVES

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The ultraviolet absorption spectra of *p*-sulphonamido-, *o*-, *m*-, *p*-methoxyphenylimino-campbors (*d*- and *dl*-) and *o*- and *p*-methoxyphenylamino-campbors (*d*- and *dl*-) have been taken with a view to comparing the 'characteristic' wave-lengths (λ_s), deduced from Drude's rotatory dispersion equation, with absorption maxima (λ_{max}), obtained by direct measurement. The rotatory dispersion of these compounds is *simple*, being represented by Drude's 'one-term' equation, and there is one 'characteristic' wave-length governing rotation for each of these compounds. The ultraviolet absorption spectra of these compounds generally show two absorption maxima, and the one near the 'characteristic' wave-length is found to differ widely from it. The differences between λ_s and λ_{max} range from 0.2 μ to 83.7 μ . An explanation of this discrepancy has been given. The nature of the racemic modifications has also been discussed.

In continuation of Parts I and II of this series (Singh and Miss Amma, *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1957, **16B**, 202) we have determined the ultraviolet absorption spectra of *p*-sulphonamido-, *o*-, *m*-, *p*-methoxy-phenylimino *d*-campbors and *o*- and *p*-methoxy-phenylamino-*d*-campbors and compared the 'characteristic' wave-lengths, calculated from Drude's rotatory dispersion equation, with the absorption maxima obtained by direct measurements.

The absorption measurements of the racemic forms of these compounds have also been taken to throw further light on the nature of these racemic modifications investigated by us earlier (Singh and Saxena, this *Journal* 1958, **35**, 103) by the application of melting point—composition method of Roozeboom.

EXPERIMENTAL

The compounds studied here were prepared and purified according to the methods already described (*loc. cit.*).

The absorption spectra were recorded in very dilute solutions of the compounds in spectroscopically pure solvents with a Beckman DU spectrophotometer. The molecular extinction coefficients were calculated from optical density at different wave-lengths, but their peak values (ϵ_{max}) corresponding to the absorption maxima, λ_{max} , only have been recorded in Table I.

FIG 2

FIG. 1

FIG. 4

FIG. 3

The ultraviolet absorption curves (Figs. 1 to 5) have been obtained by plotting the molecular extinction coefficients against wave-lengths and are shown only for methyl alcohol and ethyl alcohol; those for chloroform, being similar to those in alcohols, have been omitted to economise space.

DISCUSSION

The rotatory dispersion equation of Drude,

$$[\alpha]_{\lambda} = \sum \frac{K}{\lambda^2 - \lambda_0^2},$$

relating specific rotatory power, $[\alpha]_{\lambda}$, to wave-length, λ , at which it is determined, contains several terms in the summation, namely,

$$K'/\lambda^2 - \lambda_0'^2, K''/\lambda^2 - \lambda_0''^2, K'''/\lambda^2 - \lambda_0'''^2 \text{ etc.}$$

The characteristic wave-lengths, λ_0' , λ_0'' , λ_0''' represent the absorption bands which control rotation.

Since about 1912 this equation in its simplest form,

$$[\alpha]_{\lambda} = \frac{K}{\lambda^2 - \lambda_0^2},$$

has been used to test its validity by several workers, specially Lowry *et al.* (*Phil. Trans.*, 1927, 226A, 391; *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, 125, 1593). Whereas Lowry has shown that the rotatory dispersion could be represented by a very few Drude terms, Condon (*Rev. Mod. Phys.*, 1937, 9, 432) regards these Drude terms as having average values resulting from the combination of several terms of more fundamental significance.

Generally in the case of organic compounds, the rotatory dispersion is expressed by one-term' (*simple dispersion*) or two-terms' (*complex dispersion*) formula. The remaining terms are neglected either because they are too small or nearly cancel each other. The terms found necessary in one- or two-term equation of Drude, within limits of experimental error, thus approximately represent the main contribution to the optical activity. Expressing the rotatory dispersion by 'one-term' or 'two-term' formula in this way, it therefore only approximately represents the optical rotation. Moreover, the very small range (670.8 to 520.9 $m\mu$ for the yellow-coloured compounds and 670.8 to 435.8 $m\mu$ for the colorless compounds) of the spectrum which we have employed for the determination of rotatory dispersion does not show the discrepancies in the values calculated from one- or two-term formula and the observed values of rotatory power. It is for these reasons that there are discrepancies between the observed values of the absorption maxima, λ_{max} , and the values of the 'characteristic' wave-lengths, λ_0 s, calculated from Drude's rotatory dispersion equation.

TABLE I

Camphor derivatives.	Conc. (g./litre)	Solvents.	<i>d</i> -Isomer.		<i>dl</i> -Isomer.		λ_s from $\lambda_s - \lambda_{max}$, Drude's one-term equation. *	
			λ_{max} .	ϵ_{max} .	λ_{max} .	ϵ_{max} .		
1. <i>o</i> -Methoxyphenylimino-	0.04	MeOH	345 $m\mu$	1466.0	345 $m\mu$	1860.0	359.1	14.1
	0.05	EtOH	345	1341.5	344	1815.7	371.0	26.0
	0.04	CHCl ₃	345	1287.3	345	1646.3	364.7	19.7
2. <i>m</i> -Methoxyphenylimino-	0.04	MeOH	{ 330 248	{ 2676.1 7317.0	{ 333 248	{ 2777.8 7418.6	398.3	68.3
	0.04	EtOH	{ 333 248	{ 2710.0 7533.8	{ 333 248	{ 3042.0 7736.5	397.5	64.5
	0.04	CHCl ₃	{ 333 248	{ 3082.6 9024.3	{ 333 248	{ 3109.7 9112.4	399.3	66.3
3. <i>p</i> -Methoxyphenylimino-	0.04	MeOH	{ 345 275	{ 8129.9 6427.2	{ 344 275 228	{ 5007.8 4661.2 11788.5	408.8	63.8
	0.04	EtOH	{ 345 275 230	{ 4390.2 3638.2 8827.8	{ 345 275 228	{ 4600.2 3794.0 9403.7	410.4	65.4
	0.04	CHCl ₃	{ 345 275	{ 3965.6 3739.8	{ 345 275	{ 4679.3 4245.7	417.4	72.4
4. <i>p</i> -Sulphonamidophenyl- imino-	0.04	MeOH	{ 320 240	{ 3606.0 24000.0	{ 320 240	{ 3320.0 21600.0	398.5	78.5
	0.04	EtOH	{ 320 240	{ 2624.0 17776.0	{ 320 240	{ 2752.0 18560.0	397.6	77.6
	0.04	CHCl ₃	{ 320 248	{ 2656.0 17600.0	{ 320 ...	{ 2664.0 ...	403.7	83.7
5. <i>p</i> -Methoxyphenylamino-	0.05	MeOH	{ 312 245	{ 2828.3 14196.0	{ 312 245	{ 2266.0 11957.4	245.2	0.2
	0.05	EtOH	{ 312 246	{ 2310.2 11990.0	{ 312 245	{ 2722.2 12434.0	263.5	17.5
	0.05	CHCl ₃	{ 312 ...	{ 2980.4 ...	{ 312 ...	{ 2352.6 ...	302.6	-9.4
6. <i>o</i> -Methoxyphenylamino-	0.05	MeOH	{ ... 310	{ ... 5632.0	{ ... 310	{ ... 4625.0	208.8	-36.2
	0.05	EtOH	{ 245 310	{ 10405.0 5308.4	{ 245 310	{ 9170.0 4810.2	234.3	-10.7
	0.05	CHCl ₃	{ 245 228	{ 10112.0 4210.0	{ 246 228	{ 9500.0 4190.0		
	0.05	CHCl ₃	{ 310 245	{ 5880.4 12228.0	{ 310 246	{ 5742.5 11020.4	285.1	-24.9

* Singh and Saxena, this *Journal*, 1958, 88, 103.

We may now specifically discuss the absorption spectra of arylimino- and arylamino-camphors investigated by us.

The *o*-methoxyphenylimino-camphors show absorption maxima at 345 $m\mu$ in all the three solvents. The *para* isomer also shows this band and a second band at 275 $m\mu$ in these solvents except that it shows also a third band at about 230 $m\mu$ in methyl alcohol and ethyl alcohol. In the case of the *meta* isomer, the 345 $m\mu$ band has shifted to 333 $m\mu$ and there is the second band at 248 $m\mu$. In the *p*-sulphonamidophenylimino-camphors, the longer wave-length band has shifted to 320 $m\mu$ and the second absorption

maximum occurs at $240 \text{ m}\mu$ except in chloroform solution, in which it occurs at $248 \text{ m}\mu$. In the case of *o*- and *p*-methoxyphenylamino-camphors, the longer wave-length band occurs at $310\text{-}312 \text{ m}\mu$ besides a second band at $245 \text{ m}\mu$. The *o*-methoxyphenylamino-camphors show a third band at $228 \text{ m}\mu$ in ethyl alcohol.

The above analysis thus indicates that the conjugated chromophore,

exhibits an absorption maximum, λ_{max} , at $345 \text{ m}\mu$, but it has shifted to $310\text{-}312 \text{ m}\mu$ in the case of the corresponding amino compounds with the new chromophore,

The lower bands at $228 \text{ m}\mu$ to $248 \text{ m}\mu$ belong to the saturated molecules.

FIG. 5

The 'characteristic' wave-lengths in the case of *o*-methoxyphenylimino-*d*-camphor vary from $359 \text{ m}\mu$ to $371 \text{ m}\mu$ in the three solvents, whereas those for the *meta* and *para* isomers and *p*-sulphonamidophenylimino-*d*-camphors lie between 397.5 and $417.4 \text{ m}\mu$. These results are in agreement with those obtained by Singh and Miss Seth (this

Journal, 1956, **33**, 821) for phenyl- and chlorophenyl liminocamphors. They found that the values of the λ_{cs} of these arylimino compounds varied from 390 $m\mu$ to 400 $m\mu$ except in the case of *ortho* compound in which it was about 363 $m\mu$ and those for the corresponding arylamino compounds fluctuated between 280 and 290 $m\mu$.

We thus find similar results in the case of methoxy- and *p*-sulphonamido phenyl-iminocamphors, but the values found by us for the methoxyphenylamino-camphors are somewhat lower than those found for the analogous chlorophenylamino-camphors.

The 'characteristic' wave-lengths (λ_{cs}) deduced from Drude's 'one-term' equation, thus, differ from the absorption maxima, λ_{max} (Table I). This difference varies from 0.2 to 83.7 $m\mu$, it being more in the arylimino than in arylamino compounds. This may be explained by reasons given above.

Racemic Forms.—The ultraviolet absorption spectra of the racemic forms are found to be almost identical with those of the corresponding *dextro* forms, the differences being in the molecular extinction coefficients in the two cases.

Since the ultraviolet absorption curves of the *dextro* and *laevo* isomers of the substances are always identical, the curves for the racemic forms must also be the same if the latter occur as a mixture of the *d* and *i* forms. However, if the racemic form in solution is a racemate (*dl*-compound), its absorption curve may or may not be identical with that given separately by the antipodes.

In the solid state all these racemic forms were found to be racemic compounds (Singh and Saxena, *loc. cit.*) by the melting point—composition method of Roozeboom. Since in very dilute solutions they give curves almost identical and nearly superposable with those given by the *dextro*-forms, it may be concluded that they are almost completely dissociated in dilute solution into the optically active and opposite forms.

Further investigation in this direction, using concentrated solutions, could not be made as the solutions of even twice this strength became opaque and unsuitable in the required range of the spectrum.

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